

TRANSITION TO INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS IN UZBEKISTAN - A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIME

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Annotation: The purpose of the transition to international financial reporting standards, the need for it, the tasks and conditions to be performed are described. The article also analyzes the compliance of the National Accounting Standards (NAS) of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS).

Key words: International Financial Reporting Standards, Joint Stock Companies, Corporate Governance, International Certification of Accountants, Professional Organizations.

Introduction

The deepening processes of globalization and integration in the countries of the world lead to the transition to generally accepted international norms and standards and the growing demand for their observance. Bringing accounting and reporting in accordance with the requirements of international standards on this basis to achieve global harmonization of financial reporting, the effective use of best practices at the national level has become the most urgent problem for all countries. These issues are also relevant for Uzbekistan. Therefore, the transition to IFRS is also an urgent problem for our country, which seeks international integration and occupies a worthy place in the global economy.

The main purpose of the transition to IFRS in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to create a favorable investment climate for foreign investment, establish an effective management mechanism, improve the quality of management decisions, create conditions, opportunities and resources for company development, reduce costs and competitiveness of the company.

The introduction of international financial reporting standards, along with increasing the reliability and objectivity of information in financial statements, will serve as an important tool for attracting foreign investment into the economy of our country.

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The need to switch to international financial reporting standards is also determined by the fact that companies and organizations are required to prepare financial statements in accordance with IFRS in order to enter global markets, increase the export potential of our country, and are quoted on world commodity and currency exchanges.

The implementation of IFRS is determined by the extent to which the existing national accounting standards of Uzbekistan in our country comply with international standards. Scholars have been compared by international auditing organizations, including KPMG, with IFRS standards from a number of countries, such as Russia [7]. However, today the amount of work reflecting the results of comparing NAS of Uzbekistan with IFRS is small [9,10]. In this regard, it is important to determine the tasks arising from the regulatory legal acts on the transition to IFRS in Uzbekistan today, to form a model for the transition to IFRS, to identify areas for improving national standards based on a comparison of NAS with IFRS. This scientific article is important because it focuses on these issues..

Literature review

The legal basis for the transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) is set out in a new version of the Law on Accounting [1], adopted on 14 April 2016. Paragraph 3 of Article 10 of this Law states that "Accounting entities may apply international financial reporting standards in the manner prescribed by law." Paragraph 3 of Article 22 of the Law, which regulates financial reporting, strengthens the rule that "requirements for financial reporting based on international standards are determined by international financial reporting standards."

In order to ensure the transition to IFRS in the country, by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 24, 2015 No. PF-4720 "On measures to introduce modern corporate governance in joint-stock companies", the Resolution "On measures to reform and increase its investment attractiveness" and No. PQ- 4124 dated January 17, 2019 "On measures to further improve the activities of mining and metallurgical industries". The annual financial report was published in accordance with IFRS and was subject to external audit in accordance with International Standards on Auditing (ISA). Nowadays, there is a need for the full systematic implementation of IFRS and a special solution aimed at drastically improving training in this area.

In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 PQ-4611 "On additional measures for the transition to

international financial reporting standards [4]." The purpose of this resolution is to:

Ensuring the implementation of Articles 10 and 22 of the Law "On Accounting";

improving the investment climate for the inflow of foreign investment in our country, increasing the investment attractiveness of companies;

providing foreign investors with the necessary information, adapting the content and structure of reports to the needs of information users;

ensuring the implementation of corporate governance principles;

Expanding the access of Uzbek companies and banks to international stock and financial markets;

increase the volume of export operations of joint stock companies, holding companies and other enterprises;

increase the competitiveness of companies;

raising the system of training specialists in the field of accounting and auditing to the level of international standards.

Methods.

The research used the method of comparison of the provisions of the National Accounting Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan with IFRS, logical analysis, analysis and synthesis methods.

Results

These decisions are important documents in the development of accounting in our country. We can include the following factors in the vital conditions for the adoption of these documents in our country.

Firstly, there is a huge opportunity for foreign investment in our country. Legal environment has arisen. On December 26, 2019, a new version of the Law "On Investments and Investment Activities" [2] was adopted. The law further expanded transparency and openness, freedom of investment activities, and strengthened their guarantees. For example, in 2019 alone, "foreign direct investment amounted to \$ 4.2 billion" [3]. In order to improve the investment climate, it has become necessary for foreign investors to provide them with information on the basis of IFRS. The largest investment-intensive sectors of the country - mining and metallurgy, heavy metallurgy, chemical industry, oil extraction and refining, automotive, cotton processing and light industry - have become an important factor in achieving the development of IFRS reporting.

Secondly, access to international stock exchanges, financial (currency and capital) markets has become a vital activity for Uzbek companies to sell their products at world prices in order to expand their export potential. One of the most important and basic conditions for access to these markets is that companies, including holdings, joint-stock companies, submit their financial statements in accordance with IFRS. Commercial banks operating in our country are required to submit their reports in accordance with IFRS in order to obtain international loans and grants. IFRS reporting is required to receive funds in foreign currency from the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank and the International Monetary Fund. Today, Uzbekistan has become an active participant in this process.

Thirdly, the national accounting standards of Uzbekistan in force in our country were introduced in August 1998. These standards are largely consistent with International Accounting Standards developed before 2002. Since 2002, the IFRS Council has begun to develop International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) instead of International Accounting Standards (IAS). As a result, there is a need for direct application of IFRS for the development of national standards in accordance with IFRS developed in our country after 2002, and for active participation in the process of international unification and harmonization of accounting.

Fourth, the financial report is the main document that contains financial information in our country. Management decisions are made on the basis of these reporting data, in particular, investment decisions are also based on the reporting data. Therefore, the information in the reports is required to be objective, truthful, realistic, useful, reliable and relevant. These quality characteristics can only be achieved through the competence of qualified accountants and auditors. Certification of accountants in the formation of competence of accountants who can work on the basis of qualified IFRS, including Certified International Professional Accountant (CIPA), ACCA (The Association of Chartered Certified Accountants), Certified Public Accountant (CPA), Diploma in International Financial Reporting (DipIF) trainings. Today, the fact that Uzbekistan has its own internationally certified accountants and auditors is the most important factor in the transition to IFRS.

Fifth, Uzbekistan is gradually transitioning to an innovative economy and the digital economy. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev declared 2020 the Year of the Science, Education and Development of the Digital Economy [3]. The digital economy relies on a single database, a significant part of which is formed in accounting. Electronic integration of accounting and

management systems in a single database is a key feature of the digital economy. The formation of the accounting database is based on IFRS. Therefore, the digital economy in our country has necessitated the transition to IFRS. It is safe to say that the transition to IFRSs is an important and integral part of the digital economy.

We believe that the following measures should be taken to ensure the implementation of the tasks set by the Presidential Decree:

- Membership in the Board of IFRS and the International Federation of Accountants of Professional Organizations in the Field of Accounting and Auditing in Uzbekistan, payment of membership fees, cooperation at the state level, the creation of networks of delegations, the transition to IFRS in Uzbekistan should be recognized by international organizations;

- Official translation of IFRSs and interpretations of standards into Uzbek, achievement of official recognition of Uzbek versions of IFRSs by the IFRS Council;

- It is necessary to create a set of Uzbek terms that meet the requirements of IFRS for accounting, financial reporting and auditing, and for this it is necessary to adopt international terms, translate them into Uzbek or accept the same accepted terms in other languages without changes. Without this development, it will not be possible to professionally translate IFRS into Uzbek. For this purpose, we consider it expedient to establish a Council of professional accountants and auditors under the competent authorities;

- We must ensure that joint-stock companies, limited liability companies and other enterprises in our country voluntarily transition to financial reporting on the basis of IFRS on their own initiative. Businesses and organizations should benefit from the transition to IFRS and feel its benefits. Ensuring the financial stability of enterprises by achieving investment attractiveness using IFRS should be considered as a task of strategic importance;

- Uzbekistan's National Accounting Standards (SAS), which fully comply with IFRS, need to be reviewed. The differences between IFRS and NAS must be overcome, should coordinate as much as possible. Standards that exist in IFRS but are not included in NAS should also be developed. Interpretations of standards need to be developed. Other by-laws on accounting, including the Statutes and Regulations, should also be standardized. In Uzbekistan, a system of national accounting standards should be formed;

- In order to improve the quality of information reflected in the financial statements, to harmonize its structure and content in the interests of information users, to use the most advanced methods and techniques in information processing

and transmission, to introduce improved international financial instruments and IFRS standard financial reporting formats;

- the introduction of an effective national certification system for accountants and auditors in accordance with IFRS, the organization of educational processes and teaching aids based on international best practices in accredited training centers, ensuring the transparency of exams and evaluating results. In accordance with the requirements of the ACCA for international certification in training centers "A. basic sciences 1) the role of accountants in business; 2) management account; 3) financial account; 4) corporate and business law; 5) preparation of reports for management; 6) taxation; 7) financial reporting; 8) approval of audit and report; 9) financial management. B. Professional block 1) management, risk and ethics; 2) corporate reporting; 3) business analysis; 4) in-depth science of financial management; 5) in-depth science of preparation of reports for management; 6) in-depth science of taxation; organization of in-depth training on audit and reporting approval "[5];

- Aligning the content of accounting and auditing in higher education institutions with the curricula and programs (syllabus) of universities in developed countries, international accreditation of curricula, retraining of teachers, organization of training and exams in educational centers and foreign universities for international certification of teachers. the provision of textbooks in advanced universities;

- the organization of special IFRS programs to ensure the use of modern information technologies, the creation of all conditions for the publication of financial statements of enterprises, the creation of a website for financial reporting of Uzbek companies, the implementation of methodological assistance and the organization of reading and analysis of financial statements.

For the introduction of IFRSs, certain conditions and environment must be created in the country:

- business units, including joint-stock companies, should have a management system that meets the requirements of international standards, corporate governance principles should be introduced. International standards are set in this management system;

- the country should have independent professional accounting and auditing public organizations in addition to the competent state bodies, the composition of certified practicing accountants and auditors should be formed;

- The country should have a developed financial market, real estate market, commodity exchanges, labor market, banking and financial institutions that meet international standards. The financial activities of enterprises should become their

significant profitable activities, and a high level of development of financial instruments, including the stock market, must be ensured;

- It is desirable that the main objects of financial accounting are the emergence of mechanisms for assessing assets, liabilities, private capital, income and expenses at fair value, stable inflation in the economy, the development of organizations that are valued at fair market value. Fair value measurement is a key element of IFRS.

The implementation of the above work will ensure the implementation of the President's decision. The transition to IFRS in our country will serve to improve the investment climate, increase the investment potential of enterprises, increase the quality of personnel in the industry.

One of the most important areas of transition to IFRS is the harmonization of national accounting standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are currently in force in our country, with international standards. We can formalize their compatibility in the following table:

Table 1⁴

Comparison of national accounting standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan with international financial reporting standards

International Financial Reporting Standards	National Accounting Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting	Conceptual bases of preparation and presentation of financial statements
IAS-1 Presentation of Financial Statements	№1 NAS Accounting policy and financial reporting
IAS-2 Inventories	№4 NAS Inventory resources
IAS-7 Statement of Cash Flows	№9 NAS Cash flow statement
	№3 NAS Income statement
IAS-8 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors	№1 Provided by NAS
IAS-10 Events After the Reporting Period	№16 NAS Unforeseen circumstances and events that occurred in the business after the date of the balance sheet
IAS-12 Income Taxes	
IAS-16 Property, Plant and Equipment	№5 NAS Fixed assets
IAS-19 Employee Benefits	

⁴ Based on IFRS [6] and NAS [8].

IAS-20 Accounting for Government Grants and Disclosure of Government Assistance	№10 NAS Account of state subsidies and description of state aid
IAS-21 The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates	№22 NAS Account of assets and liabilities denominated in foreign currency
IAS-23 Borrowing Costs	№24 NAS Debt expense account
	№11 NAS Research and Development Costs
IAS-24 Related Party Disclosures	
	№14 NAS Private equity report
	№15 NAS Balance sheet
IAS-26 Accounting and Reporting by Retirement Benefit Plans	
IAS-27 Separate Financial Statements	
IAS-28 Investments in Associates and Joint Ventures	№12 NAS Молиявий инвестициялар ҳисоби (қисман мувофиқ келади)
	№17 NAS Contracts in capital construction
	№19 NAS Organization and conduct of inventory
	№20 NAS On the simplified accounting and reporting of small enterprises
IAS-29 Financial Reporting in Hyperinflationary Economies	
IAS-33 Earnings Per Share	
IAS-34 Interim Financial Reporting	
	№21 NAS Accounting chart of financial and economic activities of economic entities and instructions on its application
IAS-36 Impairment of Assets	
IAS-37 Provisions ,Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets	
IAS-38 Intangible Assets	№7 NAS Intangible assets
IAS-32 Financial Instruments: Presentation	
IAS-39 Financial Instruments : Recognition and Measurement	
IAS-40 Investment Property	

IAS-41 Agriculture	
IFRS-1 First-time Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards	
IFRS-2 Share-based Payment	
IFRS-3 Business Combinations	№23 NAS Formulation of financial statements in the implementation of the reorganization
IFRS-4 Insurance Contracts	
IFRS-5 Noncurrent Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations	
IFRS-6 Exploration for and Evaluation of Mineral Resources	
IFRS-7 Financial Instrument: Disclosure	
IFRS-8 Operating Segments	
IFRS-9 Financial Instruments	
IFRS-10 Consolidated Financial Statements	№8 NAS Consolidated financial statements and investment accounts in subsidiaries
IFRS-11 Joint Arrangements	
IFRS-12 Disclosure of Interest in Other Entities	
IFRS-13 Fair Value Measurement	
IFRS-14 Regulatory Deferral Accounts	
IFRS-15 Revenue from contracts with Customers	№2 NAS Income from basic economic activities
IFRS-16 Leases	№6 NAS Rent account
IFRS-17 Insurance contracts	

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the results of the comparison of NAS in Uzbekistan with IFRS can be divided into four groups:

The first group is the standards whose name and content are mostly consistent. These include the conceptual framework for preparing and presenting financial statements, NAS 1 “Accounting Policies and Financial Statements”, NAS 4 “Inventories”, NAS 5 “Fixed Assets”, NAS 7 “Intangible Assets”. NAS 9 “Cash Flow Statement”. In terms of the name and content of these standards, the basic rules are consistent with international standards. However, subsequent changes to IFRS in national standards are not reflected. For example, changes in the conceptual

provisions introduced in the “Conceptual Framework of Financial Reporting” from January 1, 2019 are not reflected in the national standard. Therefore, we need to work on improving the conceptual rules in our country. In addition, these standards need to be revised based on the requirements of international standards. For example, it is appropriate to include the following items in NAS 5 Property, Plant and Equipment (Table 2).

Table 2
Recommendations for the improvement of NAS 5 “Fixed Assets”

NAS 5 “Fixed Assets”	IAS-16 “Property, Plant and Equipment” стандартига мувофиқ таклиф этилади
This article is not listed in the national standard	Separate classes of property, buildings, machinery and equipment include: (a) Land; (b) land and buildings; (c) cars and equipment; (d) water bodies; (e) aircrafts; (f) motor vehicles; (g) elements of furniture and assembly engineering equipment;
This rule is not mentioned in the national standard.	The entity evaluates property, building, machinery and equipment through a cost model or a revaluation model . This selected model must be applied to the entire class of property, building, machinery and equipment. Following initial recognition as an asset, property, plant and equipment is carried at cost less accumulated depreciation and impairment losses. An item of property, plant and equipment, which is recognized as an asset at fair value, is measured at revalued amount less accumulated depreciation and accumulated impairment losses. The revaluation shall not allow a material difference between the carrying amount of the asset and the value determined at the reporting date using a fair assessment.

It is advisable to make appropriate changes to other standards in the same manner.

The second group is part of international standards, but national standards have not yet been developed to comply with it. As can be seen from the table, such standards include **IAS-12** “Income Taxes”, **IAS-19** “Employee Benefits”, **IAS-24** “Related Party Disclosures”, **IAS-26** “Accounting and Reporting by Retirement Benefit Plans”, **IAS-27** “Separate Financial. Statements”, **IAS-28** “Investments in

Associates and Joint Ventures”, **IAS-29** “Financial Reporting in Hyperinflationary Economies”, **IAS-33** “Earnings Per Share”, **IAS-36** “Impairment of Assets”, **IAS-37** “Provisions, Contingent” Standards include Liabilities and Contingent Assets, **IAS-32** “Financial Instruments: Presentation”, **IAS-39** “Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement”, **IAS-40** “Investment Property”, and **IAS-41** “Agriculture”.

Currently, the country is working on the development and submission of national standards that are consistent with these standards.

The third group of standards is the International Financial Reporting Standards, which were developed after 2002, and there are no corresponding standards. Most of the national standards in this section, as indicated in the table, were developed in 1998 and do not include subsequent changes to international standards. It is advisable to work on the development of these standards, improving existing ones.

In preparing the statement of financial position, the Company is required to make the following adjustments in accordance with IFRS 1 “First-time Adoption of IFRS”:

- a) All assets and liabilities that are recognized in accordance with IFRSs should be recognized;
- b) Articles that do not provide for recognition in accordance with IFRS should not be recognized as assets and liabilities;
- c) Reclassification of assets, liabilities and equity items in the statement of financial position in accordance with the provisions of IFRS;
- d) Carry out an assessment of assets and liabilities in accordance with IFRS [6];

Discussion and conclusions

Each company approaches the transition to IFRS at the level of its capabilities and professionalism. Based on the requirements of these standards, it is advisable for Uzbek companies to carry out the following work to ensure a quality transition to IFRS:

- Determining the date of transition to IFRS. For example, if a company prepares financial statements based on IFRS 2021, it will begin the transition to IFRSs from 31 December 2019 to generate comparative data, and this is the transition date;
- Development of IFRS accounting policies. Compliance with the requirements of IFRS 1 “First-time application of IFRS”;

- Creating a plan of working accounts on IFRS;
- Development of model, formulas, procedure, sequence, tables and postings projects according to IFRS;
- identification of subsidiaries, associates, related parties that are part of the corporate governance system of the company in cases where the preparation of consolidated financial statements is required. Preparation of their reporting systems and consolidation methods in accordance with international standards;
- determination of the currency in which the financial statements are submitted (Uzbek soum, US dollar, EURO or other state currency unit).
- monitoring the inflation process in the country, determining indices, collecting statistics;
- the list and composition of the assets, liabilities, equity, income and expenses and other items to be measured should be determined and, in some cases, should be accounted for in accordance with IFRS, even if they are not reflected in the national standard;
- components of financial reporting, including balance sheet, profit and loss statement, change in equity and cash flow statement, development of format of comments and explanations in accordance with IFRS;
- implementation of classification (reclassification) and regrouping of accounting objects in accordance with IFRS;
- assessment of accounting objects in the company on the basis of rules, principles and methods provided for in the accounting policy developed on the basis of IFRS;
- Translation of IFRS financial statements into foreign currency;
- Providing IFRS to users of information.

The implementation of this work will ensure the quality of the transition to IFRS in the country, accelerate the implementation of international standards and serve to improve the investment climate.

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